
USE AND IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND SOCIAL NETWORKS IN LIBRARIES: A REVIEW

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Abstract:

Library in the ICT era having the material other than printed books means in electronic format such as text, excel, sound, music, CD, DVD, Photos, audio, video or in many other format. In this digital era, libraries have to take support of social media and network for the distribution of information to user. Content-sharing, relations, communication, community-based input, and cooperation are collective term for websites and applications that spotlight on Social media. Contact and relation with friends, family and other people are maintained by using Social media and networks. [W 2] For marketing and promoting the products so many businesses are using social applications and also follow customer issues. Social essentials such as remark fields for users are included in Business-to-consumer websites. Businesses follow, calculate and examine brand understanding and customer views are also identified by using variety of tools from social media. Social media has a huge global appeal. These platforms are made easy to use by mobile applications. Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn are some well-liked examples of frequently used social media platforms. This paper gives the review of social media and networks used for library for user need and satisfaction of getting information in their respective subject and format.

Keywords: Social Media, Social Networks, Library Use, Library Services

Introduction:

Events and images, educate the public about services, highlight their collections, and support other libraries are shared by libraries using social media. It is challenge for libraries to support user's needs, followers and gaining staff support by using social media.

The use of social media helps create instant interaction with library users and more importantly converts non-users into library users. Social media allows the presentation of news, exhibits, etc. and reduces the information load on the library's home page.

Social Media:

“Social media is Tools for sharing and discussing information in humans mostly based on the internet.” – Wikipedia [W 7]

“Various initiatives that integrate technology, social interaction, and structure of words and Pictures commonly come under social media.” - Evil Media [W 8]

Figure 1 [W 6]

For sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through virtual networks and communities, computer-based technologies that facilitate is social media. Internet-based and quickly electronic correspondence such as personal information documents, videos, and photos is been supported by social media. With the help of computers, tablets or smart phones through web-based software or applications, Users connect with social media. [P 3]

Users can share information, ideas, personal messages, and other content (such as videos) using Social media and also communications on the Internet (such as on websites for social networking and micro-blogging) easy for users. The concepts of social networking and social media be related, but users build communities among themselves using social networking while social media is more about using social networking sites and associated platforms to put together an viewers.[W 2]

For exchange of ideas, thoughts, and information through the creation of virtual networks and communities Social Media is useful that based on computer technology. More than 4 billion users are using social media worldwide.[W 9] Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, Pinterest. Fliker and YouTube are the most commonly used social networks. User-generated content and personalized profiles are generally content of Social media. [P 3]

A dedicated web app or site that enables end users to exchange ideas and information with each other over the Internet by sharing mixed forms of information and data. Data includes images, videos, blogs, files, comments, etc. Participation in and access to online social networks is possible using a computer or mobile technology such as a phone or tablet. According to this definition the term social networking can be used to describe two, somewhat different things: a social network as a social structure (social relationship) or an online social network web site or web application (web app). [W 3]

Considering that media is the plural for media, social media is a combination of web sites and web or computer software that allows individuals to exchange ideas and various information, including but not limited to opinions and observations, notes, news, digital videos and photos and many others. End users can participate in these collaborations and use social media services if they use a mobile device, such as a phone or tablet or computer. Social media enables people to share information, communicate with others, and participate in online social networking over the Internet using their mobile devices or computers. [W 3]

Social media is used as a communication tool by libraries around the world. Reach out to library users and provide them with information at their own time and place. This gives information of social media, explored the reasons why libraries adopt social media. Libraries must create content consistent with user preferences. Content posted on social media and user interaction should always be moderated, regularly measured. In the near future, if used correctly, social media can be the primary means of

bringing libraries and their users closer together.

Advantages of using Social Media in Libraries:

- To help libraries to be closer to the users and create a joint platform for these users. Social media is a great way to be a focus for the attention of new users marketing of library resources and services. So social media creates prospective Users of the library.
- Registration is very easy for any user. Users can update their profile via their mobile phones through text messaging and downloaded apps for some smart phones and tablets. A user can create as many accounts as he wants another.
- Users can get answers to specific questions by using social media as well useful for helpful ideas and suggestions. Thus it enhances referral services.
- Friends and neighbors are using applications for rating, reviewing and sharing. Application has been made for this new method Amazon and the same can be applied for libraries.
- Messages can be sent to or from other individuals by using social media. Users can easily see the message. This is a great effort supporting the concept of reading lists generated by librarians and in some cases user-generated reading list that is more beneficial than librarians.
- Social media helps students choose and access library resources To add content to the library's website.

- It is not very expensive. User can avail social media by paying Phone service provider charges.
- Users are willing to use social media in the library and have shown their insistence For the benefits of social media in library resources and services.

A library is considered as a repository of knowledge, which stores, preserves and disseminate information. Success and efficiency of any library service Supporting research and education is defined by accurate and timely information provided to its users. Thus such information is disseminated through various means Its access is convenient for users. This millennial century that allows people to share and Share their ideas, thoughts and information. The advent of social media and its rapid growth It has now affected almost all sectors and libraries are no exception. Libraries and the role of librarians in this contemporary era is challenging, providing information Requirements of gadget freaks and tech savvy users. Social media tools play an important role in every domain especially libraries Information Science. It is a vibrant tool for promoting library products and services these days. In the current era, users are in a hands-off mode of accessing information Devices for communicating, managing and sharing information. This paper focuses on to understand the various marketing activities undertaken by libraries to promote products and Services, user participation in these social media tools used by the library. The results of this the study clearly highlights factors such as age and gender of LIS professionals On using social media tools for marketing library products and services. To meet outside Social media

over time has a huge impact on the expectations of the user community

accessing the current requirements of the user community. [P 6]

Social Networking:

Figure 2 [W 4]

Online social networks and blogs are two leading Web 2.0 technologies that can be adopted as part of online services in libraries. The basic structure, additional features and new emerging trends in the field of social networking services had been highlighted with impact on society. Different types of domains are working for social networking. It can also be used for network information distribution. New generation users can access library services at their own place and time through library profiles on these networks. To improve the position of library and LIS professionals in society in today's busy digital age, social networking is one of the best mediums, as most of the internet users are frequenting social networking sites. And this is the best way to strengthen the marketing of library services as well as the library and LIS profession and professionals. Many libraries are using it for marketing of library services, promoting events, book review, user support, CAS, SDI, reference desk, library consortia etc. Advantages and

disadvantages of these social networking tools are also mentioned.[P 4]

Academia.edu is a similar source that allows users to create, upload personal profiles documents, request feedback, follow researchers, send personal messages to other researchers and view analyzes on your papers. Users on Academia.edu can bring in contacts from Facebook, Twitter, Yahoo and Google to find colleagues who already have an Academia.edu profile connecting several different networking devices described. Academic.edu is a professional social networking site for researchers. A researcher can create a profile, upload and select their work Areas of interest to find a network of users with similar interests. Analytics related to engagement Available with uploaded research.

Google Scholar provides a search engine that can be used to identify hyperlinks Articles that are freely available or can be obtained through institutional libraries. Users who choose to create a personal Google Scholar profile to access citation

metrics per year. Articles uploaded to ResearchGate, Academia.edu or other databases may be linked to you. Google Scholar Profile so readers can find hyperlinks to all scholarly work.

ResearchGate is a professional social networking site for researchers. is a researcher Able to create profiles, share documents, engage in discussions and find collaborators. There are also some metrics available specifically for this platform.

Mendeley: Academics may be familiar with Mendeley as a reference manager, but it functions as an educational social network. Researcher can develop profile, share Research papers, and contact researchers. Mendeley was acquired by Elsevier in 2013. [P 5]

Figure 3 [W 4]

Face Book: Different types of information can be provided to the library users with the help of Face Book such as share information about upcoming events and their new arrivals and book releases. Facebook mainly helps in marketing of services and products. It is also used for tagging photographs. It can be availed by using Ask-A – Librarian service.

Twitter: Twitter is a free social networking used for sending and reading messages Tweets currently share all kinds of library news from end to end librarians twitter. Librarians can highlight new materials, new groups, meetings, and some of these suggestions via twitter.

LinkedIn: It is a professional networking site. Librarians use it to prepare professional relations among other library professionals and to market library

services spread across the globe and can also share their ideas and business experiences.

Web 2.0: The term was coined by Darcy DiNuccie in 1999 and popularized by Tim O'Reilly 4. Weblogs, wikis, and syndication are the included terms. It is almost identical including social media.

Blogs: Blogs can be used by libraries to keep their users aware of the latest developments in related areas. Blogs can be subscribed to via RSS feed. Blogger and Word Press are examples of blogs.

Benefits of social networking while sitting in the library:

- a) To captures prospective users of the library.
- b) To offers more than conventional ways of marketing library services.

- c) To helps users to use the library effectively.
- d) To allow the user to create, connect, converse, contribute, choose and share information.
- e) It helps libraries to be closer to users.
- f) It helps libraries to build collaborative networks with users.
- g) To grab the interest of new users.
- h) It helps students find library resources.
- i) It facilitates knowledge sharing.
- j) To inform users. [P 10]

Libraries are service centers that aim to make available focused, present and proper services to their users. Achieving the goals of libraries, technology has emerged as a key aspect. Libraries are always at the forefront of incorporating emerging technologies into their setups. With the rise of Web 2.0, libraries also moved towards the concept of Library 2.0. Library 2.0 incorporates Web 2.0 tools, thus facilitating an environment that is user-centered and connects diverse academic communities, eventually progressing to a critical institution designed to meet user needs and the current information culture (Scott, 2013). The latest in trend is social media. Libraries are already in the race to adopt this new technology. Smart screens packed with features and social media apps have already reached billions of people around the world. Social media are cheap and cost-effective tools for library services with increasing needs and shrinking budgets. These tools are used by libraries for customer service, news and updates, content/collection promotion, dissemination of the institution's research output, provision of educational tools and resources, and building relationships within and outside the institution. The use

of social media in libraries has grown speedily. This service is used by libraries to disseminate and promote services, programs and new resources, as well as to provide general information. Distance learning and knowledge sharing may include additional profit. [P 7]

Conclusion:

Social media helps library professionals increase their ability to build better relationships between library staff and library users for themselves and their readers. Social media like Facebook help library professionals create accounts to promote their library resources and services. Facebook provides a platform to market their resources and services effectively and efficiently. In the present age of information explosion, human frame of mind and thoughts have been changed. Everyone is in a row after information, but they do not know how to collect information and share information one to one and one to many at a time. Apart from these facts, ICT and its interconnected aids have changed the role of information professionals in the current information age. Social media has produced surroundings where everyone can access, exchange and disseminate information. In addition, many social networks have been launched and some of them are very popular worldwide like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, WeChat, Instagram, Twitter, Telegram, LinkedIn, Snapchat, Pinterest, Viber etc. People reach out to and share their information with others across long distances with help of Social media. In the 21st century there is an explosion of information and data is available in different formats. Users looking for information related to content in their field of study. There are best practices support aspects for the library to

provide more relevant services to the user. In this paper, social media and social networks useful for academics Libraries are explained and followed to meet user needs and expectations.

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